

Effect Of HRM Practices On Job Satisfaction In The Higher Education Sector Of Balochistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 05, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Employee Satisfaction, HRM Practices, Recruitment And Selection, Training And Development, Performance Appraisal, Higher Education Institutes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5978993</p>	<p><i>At present, developing job satisfaction (JS) among the employees has become the central issue of the organizations. The present paper aims to examine the effect of human resource management (HRM) practices on JS among the employees of higher education institutes of Balochistan. The study is quantitative. Therefore, it utilizes the cross-sectional data to reach the purpose of the study. The study applies a survey questionnaire and collects the facts from the participants randomly. In total, 330 valid samples are utilized to infer the outcomes. By employing the path analysis, the study reveal positive significant impact on JS of HR practices, i.e. recruitment and selection (RaS), training and development (TaD) and performance appraisal (PA). The outcomes of the research would upkeep the policymakers and top management in bringing more JS culture through HRM practices among the employees, especially within the higher education institutes. Finally, the study's outcomes would further deepen human resource management literature, mostly in developing nation settings.</i></p>

Introduction

Creating happiness and JS among the employees is a big challenge for almost every organization in the corporate world. To tackle such the issue, HRM practices play a robust and construct role. According to Javed *et al.* (2019), HRM practices such as **RaS**, **PA**, **TaD**, and provision of suitable training are responsible for developing the satisfaction and commitment among the employees. These are considered the planned strategy for all management initiatives that influence the association between the company and its employees. In the perception of Beer *et al.* (1984), human resources are the vital and favourable factors for the growth of organizations and progress. Therefore, it is not only the need of the local organizations but also a global need to assume good HRM practices for maintaining a skilled and competent workforce. Through this can improve organizational efficiency significantly. Danish and Usman (2010) suggest that organizations must implement good practices and follow a planned strategy to reinforce HRM by developing a competitive advantage (Khan, 2010). However, several firms concentrate on Total Quality Management (TQM) to stay ahead of the rivalry, and hence superintend the standing of staff and overall human resource competence in the organization's growth and progress (Khera, 1999). On the other hand, unsuccessful HRM activities decline employee satisfaction and, as a consequence, disturb their loyalty to the business. In the competitive environment of the day, intangible assets, i.e. intellectual capital, must be kept operational to promote companies and related essentials (Malik *et al.* 2010). Higher educational institutions envisioned for both study and teaching must concentrate on, retain, and support the promotion and growth of workers and progressively handle competitive advantages for achieving organizational goals. Consequently, universities must recruit a well-trained and motivated workforce for conducting research and training more professionally and efficiently (Lew, 2009). Several investigations highlight that better HRM practices allow university employees to be more affianced in their work, which is vital for the success of the institutions (Shahzadet *al.*, 2008; Chen *et al.*, 2009; Shah & Soomro, 2021). The present study examines the stimulus of HRM practices on JS among the employees of higher education institutes of Balochistan. The study findings would be supportive for management agents to develop and bring more satisfaction among the employees.

Literature review, model and hypotheses

Examining JS through HRM practices is the need of every organization, predominantly in higher education institutes. In Peshawar, Pakistan, Javed *et al.* (2019) demonstrates a significant and positive role of

the HRM practices in creating JS among the faculty members. An empirical study conducted by Soomro and Shah (2019) found organizational commitment and JS as the robust and active forecasters of the performance of employees. Further, entrepreneurial orientation is also found the analyst of organizational commitment. In the context of Thailand, students' satisfaction can develop through providing the best qualities in terms of service, administration, and environmental (Ali *et al.*, 2019). In the Pakistani nursing domain, by employing the SEM analysis, Bhatti *et al.* (2021a) provide evidence of a positive association of performance goal and cognitive ability with employees' performance rather than a significant connection between motivation to learn and perform. According to Gamage (2014), **RaS** are vigorous utilities of human resource management for any business firm. The factors such as learning style and training content significantly forecast employee performance (Bhatti *et al.*, 2021b). Opatha (2010) claims that recruitment is a suitable mode of discovery and fascinating appropriately qualified individuals to apply for job posts in the institute. It is like a bunch of activities that attract job candidates who require attitudes and abilities. **According to Soomro and Shah (2021), strategic factors such as organizational learning, organizational innovation** are responsible for developing and achieving a healthy organizational performance in Pakistan. In the perception of Shah and Soomro (2021), proactive environmental strategies, internal green integration are accountable for creating the link between environmental performance and innovation. Soomro and Shah (2020) claim a substantial relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, strategic entrepreneurship and performance. In the Balochistan province of Pakistan, socio-economic factors have a vital role in enhancing students' academic performance (Soomro *et al.*, 2019).

Consequently, the domain literature offers various factors responsible for enhancing the employees' satisfaction. However, these variables are tested in different contexts and organizations from time to time. But in Balochistan's higher education institutes need more concentration in terms of empirical testing. Based on relationships and evidence deficiency, we formulated a model (Figure 1) for confirming in the higher educational institutes of Balochistan.

In academia, improving the employees and their performance always remains the protagonist problem of the institutes. Henceforth, the investigation of JS is in favour of organizations to get enhanced performance. According to Jevedet *et al.* (2019), the **RaS** procedure is the best option for organizations. Ultimately, it improves JS, and thus performance is possible. It is the best choice of HRM in the organizations. An empirical study by Gurbuz (2009) highlights an influential role of HRM practices (contingent compensation, empowerment, job rotation, participation and self-directed work teams) in increasing employees' JS. Likewise, Iqbal *et al.* (2011) support a positive and significant diversification in HRM practices in both private and public universities. According to Majumder (2012), JS and HRM practices among academic staff in government and private sector universities are positively and significantly associated. In a comparable domain, the study of Mumtaz *et al.* (2011) suggests a dynamic process in the Indian higher educational institutes. The study underlines that HRM practices, i.e. employee PA practices, compensation practices, empowerment practices, and promotion, have no significant effect on employees' JS.

Similarly, remuneration and development, job status, apprentices and management support significantly enhance job performance among academic staff (Al-Hinai&Bajracharya, 2014). By applying the survey questionnaire, the research of Ekwoaba *et al.* (2015) finds the significant effect of **RaS**Criteria on organizational performance. According to Appelbaum *et al.*(2000), HRM practices are planned to upsurge JS. In public higher institutes of Ghana, **RaS**enhance JS and performances among employees. In a conclusion, the literature supports the significant influence of **RaS**on JS(Ekwoaba *et al.*, 2015; Iqbal *et al.*, 2011; Soomro and Shah, 2021). Based on relationships, we projected:

H1. RaS positively and significantly predict JS.

The different factors HRM practices such as job rotation, empowerment, participation, compensation and teamwork significantly enhance the employee's JS(Gurbuz, 2009). Iqbal *et al.* (2011) found a substantial difference in HRM practices in both private and public universities. Although, the PA practices are the best in the private institutes than the public sector higher institutes. These findings are also supported by Majumder (2012) and found a meaningful positive influence of job design, compensation package, career growth, **RaS**systems, job security, **TaD**, work environment on JS. Besides, a significant and robust effect of HRM practices on JS is claimed by Mumtaz *et al.* (2011) in India's government and private sector universities.

Similarly, Al-Hinai and Bajracharya (2014) underline a significant impact of remuneration and development and management support on JS of academic staff in a Higher Education Institution of Oman. The study of Qazi and Jeet (2017) demonstrates that the academic staff of government educational institutes are gratified with the overall HRM practices to a modest extent. The study has claimed a higher level of satisfaction with teamwork, training, and employee participation.

On the other hand, employees looked less pleased with PA and compensations. According to Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016), **TaD**significantly predict JS in the education sector. Among Vietnamese universities, young employee retention negatively affects job performance and JS (Nguyen & Duong, 2020). Based on the evidence of positive relationships, we developed:

H2. TaD positively and significantly predicts JS.

PA is a significant factor of HRM practices, primarily for organizations. However, JS depends on the organization PA system due to its relation with an optimistic attitude and feeling towards the job. The findings of Saleem and Shah (2015) show that employees who are satisfied with their PA of the institute are delighted with their job and highly commit themselves to attain organizational objectives and goals. In a simple sense, the PA system has a meaningful and substantial impact on JS. The regression analysis of Wahjono *et al.* (2016) shows a predictive power of PA towards JS. According to researchers like Heneman and Wemer (2005), Dechev (2010), PA has a good reputation in encouraging employees' inconsequential performance cycle. The PA process is frequently inspired by an organizational necessity to impact employees' attitudes, behaviours, and organizational performance.

Most of the economies, including Malaysia, Turkey, USA, Netherland, UK, Singapore, Bangladesh, Pakistan and many more, highlight the significant prominence of PA in the various sectors, i.e. education, telecommunication, banking, NGOs and health (Saleem & Shah, 2015; Chaudhary & Bhaskar, 2016; Soomro *et al.*, 2019; Shah & Soomro, 2021). However, in educational institutes of Balochistan, it needs more confirmation. Thus:

H3. PA positively and significantly predicts JS.

Methods

The study is quantitative that employs cross-sectional facts. The random sampling practice was applied to trace the respondents. We selected the different higher education institutes of Balochistan, Pakistan. The targeted respondents were the faculty members who were performing their duties of teaching and research. We employed the survey questionnaire to get the quantitative response. Before handing over the survey to the respondents, we determined their willingness to participate in the study voluntarily. Initially, we piloted a pilot test to confirm the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. As a result, we overall found the satisfactory Cronbach's alpha (>0.70) with excellent individual's factor reliability. Besides, the content and design of the survey were also appreciated and reviewed by the field experts. We adopted all the items from well-known scholars like Saleem and Shah (2015), Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016), Soomro *et al.* (2019), Shah and Soomro (2021). All the items of scales are evaluated through a five-point Likert scale (completely agree=1; agree=2; neither agree nor disagree=3; disagree=4 and completely disagree=5).

Data analysis and results

Reliability assessment

We assess the items' internal through Cronbach's alpha (α). The total alpha is noted as 0.867, which is considered to be exceptional (>0.70) (Hair *et al.*, 2017). Nonetheless, it is noted for **RaS** as 0.889. **TaD** factor was witnessed for 0.872 (Table 1). Likewise, the consistency among the items of the PA factor is 0.826. Finally, the dependent variable (JS) has appeared with 0.830 consistency (Table 1).

Table 1. Reliability assessment

S.No.	Variables	Cronbach's alpha (α)
1	RaS	0.889
2	TaD	0.872
3	PA	0.826
4	JS	0.830

Note: RaS= Recruitment and selection; TaD= Training and development; PA=Performance appraisal; JS=Job satisfaction

Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation

We observed the descriptive statistics for ensuring the demographic trends of the respondents. We noted the maximum mean score for PA(M=3.45), JS (M=3.39), RaS(M=3.34) and TaD(M=3.09) (Table 2). Besides, the study shows the maximum standard deviation scores as PA(SD=0.96), JS (SD=0.91), RaS(SD=0.90) and TaD(SD=0.88) (Table 2). Pearson's correlation scores show the excellent correlation between independent factors and dependent factors (**)(Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and correlation co-efficient

Variables	M	SD	RaS	TaD	PA	JS
RaS	3.34	0.90	----			
TaD	3.09	0.88	0.337**	----		
PA	3.45	0.96	0.437**	0.398**	----	
JS	3.39	0.91	0.387**	0.426**	0.440**	----

Note: M=mean; SD=standard deviation; **=Correlations are significant at 0.01 and 0.05 levels, respectively (two-tailed)

Hypotheses assessment

Before hypotheses evaluation, we observed the model fit indices (fitness of model with data). The scores of CMIN= χ^2 /chi-square (2.180) ensured the total fitness of the model (Table 3). Moreover, other indicators of fitness, i.e. GFI=0.909; AGFI=0.918; NFI=0.927; CFI=0.939 and RMSEA= 0.020 are found to be within the satisfactory ranges (Figure 2 and Table 3).

Concerning hypotheses testing, we observe a significant and substantial influence of RaS on JS (SE=0.043, CR=5.672***; $p < 0.01$) among the employees of higher institutes of Balochistan (Figure 2 and Table 4). Henceforth, H1 is accepted. Likewise, the SE and CR scores also reinforced the significant positive influence of TaDon JS(SE=0.060, CR=6.692***; $p < 0.01$). Consequently, H2 is supported by the data (Figure 2 and Table 4). Lastly, the path analysis also found a positive and predictive power of PAon JS(SE=0.058, CR=6.009***; $p < 0.01$). Consequently, the final hypothesis is supported (Figure 2 and Table 4).

Table 3. Model fit indicators

	CMIN/df	GFI	AGFI	NFI	CFI	RMSEA
Model fit indicators	2.180	0.909	0.918	0.927	0.939	0.020
Suggested values	< 3	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	> 0.90	< 0.05

Note: CMIN= χ^2 /Chi-square/df; df= degree of freedom; GFI=goodness of fit index; AGFI=adjusted goodness of fit index; NFI= normed fit index; CFI= comparative fit index; RMSEA=root mean square error of approximation

Figure 2. Path analysis

Table 4. Path analysis

H.No.	Independent variables	Path	Dependent variable	Estimate	SE	CR	P	Decision
H1	RaS	→	JS	0.278	0.043	5.672	***	Accepted
H2	TaD	→	JS	0.225	0.060	6.692	***	Accepted
H3	PA	→	JS	0.356	0.058	6.009	***	Accepted

Note: SE=standard error; CR=critical ratio; p=significance level ***p<0.05

Discussion and conclusion

The purpose of the investigation was to investigate the effect of HRM practices on employee satisfaction among the employees of higher education institutes of Balochistan. Thus, we applied the quantitative mode of enquiry to serve the aim and purpose of the study. Concerning H1, the path analysis supported the positive influence of *RaSo* on JS (H1 supported). In the literature, these outcomes are supported by several scholars like Appelbaum *et al.* (2000), Iqbal *et al.* (2011), Ekwoaba *et al.* (2015), Soomro and Shah, (2021), who claimed the same results in the different contexts and institutes. The present findings underline the significant importance of *RaSo* employees in the higher education sector of Balochistan. The findings further ensure and validate that the *RaSo* merit create JS among the employees and those employees earn and perform well towards the success of their organizations. Besides, the study provides evidence of a positive association between *TaD* and job performance. Likewise, such outcomes are also in line with numerous earlier investigations, i.e. Al-Hinai and Bajracharya (2014), Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016), Qazi and Jeet (2017), who found similar results accordingly. The study proves that the academic staff of government educational institutes are happy with the overall HRM practices to an uncertain extent. They are satisfied by providing suitable and practical training, which further encourage

them to contribute to positive change and performance for the organization. Lastly, the path analysis supported the momentous influence of *PA* on *JS* (H3 accepted). These findings also concur with domain studies like Saleem and Shah (2015), Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016), Soomro *et al.* (2019), Shah and Soomro (2021), who proposed the same outcomes in various contexts, including European and Asian countries. In conclusion, the inclusive findings underlined a positive significant influence of HRM practices (*RaS*, *TaD* and *PA*) on *JS* among the employees of higher education institutes of Balochistan, Pakistan.

The study contains certain limitations. The conclusion of findings is based on a single source of data collected through a questionnaire. The study did not use any theory of HRM and *JS*. We used only three factors: *RaS*, *TaD* and *PA* to predict *JS*. The study concluded on samples of 330 employees only. In future, more longitudinal data should gather to strengthen the same model. Other sectors such as health and SMEs sectors should be considered in future studies.

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